

Optimization of electrochemical performance of NMC cathode via adjacent synthesis and test protocols

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LiNi_xMn_yCo_{1-x-y}O₂ (so-called NMC) has demonstrated the most effective combination of nickel, manganese, and cobalt for the cathode materials to yield better performance in terms of specific energy and power density, life span, costs and safety at Li-ion Batteries-LiB [1]. Nickel is responsible for high energy density and good storage capacity of LiBs, but suffers from low thermal stability and insufficient cycle life [2]. Considering these deficiencies, the NMC compositions are designed to include Manganese which acts not only as a stabilizer, but also prevents Nickel oxidation and thus, reduces the risk of capacity fading. Moreover, a new generation of cathode microparticles have been emerged aiming in a clever integration of Manganese in NMC morphologies by their core/shell structured designed synthesis. This special morphology provides surface stabilization of Ni-rich NMC by Manganese rich shell, to keep the energy storage capabilities at a higher level and thus, preventing the early cathode degradation. The strong dependence of the NMC cathode's functional properties on the relative ratios of the involved transition metals as well as the insufficient understanding of the synergistic effect of core and shell during the electrochemical tests, forced the researches to explore new synthesis approaches to enhance the overall performance of cathodes with this new structural design.

In this work, the cathode powders having Ni-rich Core/Mn-rich Shell have been synthesized via a cost efficient and easy controlled process that is built on a two-step co-precipitation method by optimization of process parameters under steady performance tests. These include variation of synthesis steps, co-precipitation agents, Li-infiltration approaches, heat

treatment conditions as well as establishment of the proper synthesis protocols to fabricate NMC cathodes with a good electrochemical performance for Li-ion batteries. In order to identify the morphological, dimensional, structural and compositional relations within the core/shell particles SEM, EDX and XRD techniques have been employed. It has been shown that thermal treatment (temperature, duration, heating rate) slightly effect the morphology of the obtained particles, however relying on to the generated XRD analysis, plays a significant role in the achievement of the best NMC crystalline phase composition by avoiding undesirable for batter performance compounds. In turn, it is observed that a likely non-efficient Li-infiltration results in poor electrochemical performances. Electrochemical characterization by means of EIS spectroscopy and CV tests indicated that the combination of crystalline phase composition, the presence of the residual Li-based compounds, as well as Li incorporation approach has a high impact on the electrochemical properties of the obtained core/shell structured NMC cathode powder.

References

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